

Perception of Brazilian researchers in the field of “Agronomy” on the role of the corresponding author

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Introduction

Essential for Brazil's economic growth, research in Agricultural Sciences has been the focus of investments and one of the most productive, efficient, and sustainable areas of national science (Glänzel, Leta & Thijs, 2006; Adams & King, 2009). Its strength stems from the liveliness of a research system composed of state institutions, universities, and, more recently, private institutions. Agricultural Sciences output has steadily outgrown global Brazilian national scientific production in the Web of Science database (Vargas, Vanz & Stumpf, 2015). Scientific collaboration is one of the factors related to the increase in scientific production. In the context of collaborative scientific production, the influence of the corresponding author (identified as a proxy of scientific leadership) comes into play in the scientific impact of articles published by institutions or countries (González-Alcaide et al., 2017; Chinchilla-Rodríguez et al., 2016). Grácio et al. (2020) observed that the impact increases by 68.1% when the Brazilian author is not the corresponding author. Vanz & Docampo (2022) observed that collaboration with at least one of the four largest English-speaking countries (Australia, Canada, the United Kingdom, and the United States) favored the number of citations received by 57.7% for the 25 most productive Brazilian institutions.

Previous results (Vanz et al., 2022) showed a noticeable growth in the number of documents in collaboration in the field of Agronomy from 2005 to 2019 and a higher normalized citation impact in the articles published with international cooperation. Within the scope of international collaboration, they

found a positive association for non-academic institutions between the corresponding authorship position and the impact of their scientific production. This study aims to characterize the perception of Brazilian researchers in the field of Agronomy on the issue of the corresponding authorship (CA) through a comparative analysis by type of institutional affiliation (university or non-university). The study focuses on the criteria that Brazilian researchers (and their research team) use to assign the role of the corresponding author of a co-authored article and the position they consider the corresponding author should occupy.

Methods

We surveyed Brazilian researchers from universities and non-academic institutions who published documents on the Web of Science in the Agronomy subject category from 2005 to 2019. Some 380 researchers completed the survey, of which 263 showed an affiliation with universities (UNIV) and 117 with non-academic institutions (N_UNIV). We constructed two contingency tables in which the researchers' responses were recorded, by type of institution, regarding the two questions analyzed: criteria for attributing the CA and the position that the CA should assume in the byline. We then conducted Chi-square tests to evaluate the difference in the perceptions of researchers affiliated with UNIV and N_UNIV institutions regarding the two

criteria. The p-values were found statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

Results

Table 1 presents the criteria used by researchers from UNIV and N_UNIV institutions in assigning the role of the corresponding author, in which we can observe that there is no significant difference between researchers by type of institution with any of the indicated criteria.

Table 1. Criteria used by researchers to assign the role of corresponding author of a co-authored article, by type of institution.

Criteria to assign the role of CA	UNIV	N_UNIV	p-val
Advisor/supervisor	52.9%	50.4%	0.66
The researcher who most contributed to the study, no matter the seniority	48.3%	49.6%	0.82
The most recognized researcher in the field	19.8%	26.5%	0.14
The researcher in charge funding for the project	17.8%	18.8%	0.83
The researcher with greater fluency in the language of the journal	15.2%	10.3%	0.20
The researcher with greater social and communication skills	13.7%	10.3%	0.35
The head or coordinator of the laboratory, research group or center	12.6%	12.8%	0.94
The technologically skilled researcher	11.4%	11.1%	0.93
The most senior researcher	7.2%	7.7%	0.87
The researcher responsible for paying the APC	4.2%	2.6%	0.44
One of the foreign researchers	0.8%	1.7%	0.40
No opinion	2.7%	5.1%	0.22

Regardless of the type of institution, to most survey respondents being the researcher who advised/supervised the research constitutes the principal criterion for attributing the role of CA. Being the researcher responsible for the most substantial contribution in the elaboration of the article is also a very relevant criterion for this community to attribute the authorship of correspondence, even if the researcher does not have the highest seniority.

Table 2 presents the respondents' perception of the position in the byline that the corresponding author should occupy, showing no statistically significant difference between researchers by type of institution. Although the perception that the CA should occupy any position in the byline was the most common, the sum of the figures related to the categories involving the first or last position in the byline configures the highest percentage, amounting to more than half of

the indications among the researchers from N_UNIV institutions.

Table 2. Position the corresponding author should occupy, by type of institution.

CA position in the byline	UNIV	N_UNIV
Any position	40.0%	32.8%
First author	20.4%	19.0%
Last author	16.2%	19.0%
First or Last author	11.2%	16.4%
Intermediate author	8.1%	7.88%
No opinion	4.2%	5.2%

$\chi^2 = 3.52$; $fd=6$; $p\text{-valor} = 0.74$

Final Considerations

The results show that the community participating in the study associates a prominent role with the corresponding author (CA), which should be held by the author who most contributed to the development of the research work or the most experienced researcher (advisor/supervisor of the research project). Furthermore, this result seems to echo the position that the CA must occupy in the byline, indicated by most respondents as being the first or last position. We also observed that these results are independent of the type of institution in which the researchers work.

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